

IDENTIFICATION OF INTERPHASE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES WITH THE VIRTUAL FIELDS METHOD: NUMERICAL SIMULATIONS

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ABSTRACT

The mechanical properties of composite materials depend on the mechanical response of the matrix, of the fibres and of the interphase. Characterizing independently the two first ones is possible through tensile tests. It is even rather easy for the matrix. The mechanical properties of the last phase, that is the interphase, remain generally unknown. The reason is the lack of suitable experimental procedures to characterize such small parts of composites. Indeed, the interphase takes place during the polymerization of the matrix and it is not possible to manufacture specific specimens made of the constitutive material of the interphase only. The only way to reach relevant information on interphase properties is to perform *in situ* tests. Microindentation is an example of procedure which leads to the local hardness of this type of materials.

The procedure proposed in the present work is based on a full-field measurement processing. The idea is to capture the kinematic field which takes place around a fibre during a tensile test carried out on a composite specimen. Such information can be obtained in practice using a microscope and a non-contact displacement measurement system like digital image correlation or grid method. The local strain field is obviously heterogeneous because of the local heterogeneity of the material. This field information is then processed with a suitable method called the Virtual Fields Method. This method has been developed during the last decade to determine mechanical properties of materials (among which composite materials) [1][2][3][4][5] for instance. This method is based on the use of the principle of the virtual work with suitable virtual fields. It has been shown that the parameters to be determined are in fact the solutions of a linear system built up with this principle.

The aim of this paper is to examine the capabilities of this method to identify local properties of interphases. The theoretical backgrounds of the method will first be given. Then, numerical simulations illustrate the accuracy and the stability of the method.

KEY TERMS: Interphase, Mechanical properties, Identification, Virtual fields method, Special virtual fields

INTRODUCTION

The purpose of this paper is to propose an original approach for the determination of mechanical parameters of an interphase between fibres and matrix in a composite. In general, mechanical properties of the interphase remain unknown. This is due to the fact that it is not possible to manufacture specific specimens made of the constitutive material of the interphase. The procedure proposed in the present work is based on the use of the virtual fields method developed during the last decade to determine mechanical properties of materials (see [1][2][3][4][5] for instance). The idea is to capture the kinematic field around a fibre by using a microscope and a non-contact displacement measurement during a tensile test carried out on a composite specimen. In the present paper, the kinematic fields are obtained with finite element simulations.

The capabilities of the method are examined for several mechanical behaviours of the interphase: elastic linear orthotropic, elastic linear isotropic and elastic linear isotropic with gradient properties. The accuracy and the stability of the method are then illustrated.

THEORY

Let us consider a composite specimen of any shape subjected to an in-plane loading (see Fig. 1). V , S and th are respectively the volume, the external surface and the thickness of the specimen. V_m , V_f and V_i are respectively the volume of the matrix, the fibres and the interphase. S_m , S_f and S_i are respectively the external surface of the matrix, the fibres and the interphase. Let us consider an orthotropic linear relationship for all the constituents that is the fibres, the matrix and the interphase. In the orthotropic axes, the stress/strain relations for each constituent i (fibre (f), interphase (i), matrix (m)) may be written in polar coordinates:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_r \\ \sigma_\theta \\ \sigma_{r\theta} \end{bmatrix}_i = \begin{bmatrix} Q_{rr} & Q_{r\theta} & 0 \\ Q_{r\theta} & Q_{\theta\theta} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & Q_{ss} \end{bmatrix}_i \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_r \\ \varepsilon_\theta \\ \varepsilon_{r\theta} \end{bmatrix}_i \quad (1)$$

Fig.1 Plate of any shape under in-plane loading

Let us suppose that the mechanical characteristics of the fibres and the matrix are known. The goal here is to identify Q_{rr} , $Q_{\theta\theta}$, $Q_{r\theta}$ and Q_{ss} in the interphase from the heterogeneous strain/stress fields that take place in the specimen. The global equilibrium of the specimen may be written as:

$$\sum_i \left(\int_{V_i} \boldsymbol{\sigma} : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^* dV \right) = \sum_i \left(\int_{S_{f_i}} \mathbf{T} \mathbf{u}^* dS \right) \quad (2)$$

For the sake of simplicity, let us suppose that vector \mathbf{u}^* is zero over S_f . Introducing the stress/strain relationship (1) in the above equation and assuming that the constitutive materials are homogeneous, the principle of virtual work may be written as:

$$Q_{ij}^{(i)} \int_{V_i} \varepsilon_i \varepsilon_j^* dV = - \left(Q_{ij}^{(f)} \int_{V_f} \varepsilon_i \varepsilon_j^* dV + Q_{ij}^{(m)} \int_{V_m} \varepsilon_i \varepsilon_j^* dV \right) \quad (3)$$

Any different virtual field provides a new linear equation of the type of Eq. (3). The so-called VFM (Virtual Fields Method) consists in writing the above equation with as many different virtual fields as unknowns. This leads to a system of linear equations:

$$\mathbf{PQ} = \mathbf{R} \quad (4)$$

where \mathbf{P} is a square matrix and \mathbf{Q} is a vector which components are the $Q_{ij}^{(i)}$'s. The choice of the virtual fields is one of the key-points of the method. The VFM can be used with so-called special virtual fields [6] that render the matrix of the linear system equal to unity, leading therefore to the direct identification of the unknown parameters. These special virtual fields are denoted hereafter $\hat{\mathbf{u}}^*, \hat{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^*$. The principle of virtual work is used with special virtual fields in such a way that three of the four $\int_{V_i} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_i \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_j^* dV$'s are zero whereas the fourth is equal to 1 m^3 . This leads to a direct

determination of the parameter which coefficient is 1 in Eq (3). For instance, if $Q_{rr}^{(i)}$ is the parameter to be extracted from the heterogeneous actual field, one can write:

$$Q_{rr}^{(i)} = -(Q_{ij}^{(f)} \int_{V_f} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_i \hat{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}_j^{*(1)} dV + Q_{ij}^{(m)} \int_{V_m} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_i \hat{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}_j^{*(1)} dV) \quad (5)$$

The other unknowns are found with the same procedure. Thus:

$$Q_{\theta\theta}^{(i)} = -(Q_{ij}^{(f)} \int_{V_f} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_i \hat{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}_j^{*(2)} dV + Q_{ij}^{(m)} \int_{V_m} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_i \hat{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}_j^{*(2)} dV) \quad (6)$$

$$Q_{r\theta}^{(i)} = -(Q_{ij}^{(f)} \int_{V_f} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_i \hat{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}_j^{*(3)} dV + Q_{ij}^{(m)} \int_{V_m} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_i \hat{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}_j^{*(3)} dV) \quad (7)$$

$$Q_{ss}^{(i)} = -(Q_{ij}^{(f)} \int_{V_f} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_i \hat{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}_j^{*(4)} dV + Q_{ij}^{(m)} \int_{V_m} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_i \hat{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}_j^{*(4)} dV) \quad (8)$$

$\hat{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^{*(1)}$, $\hat{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^{*(2)}$, $\hat{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^{*(3)}$ and $\hat{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^{*(4)}$ directly provide $Q_{rr}^{(i)}$, $Q_{\theta\theta}^{(i)}$, $Q_{r\theta}^{(i)}$ and $Q_{ss}^{(i)}$ respectively. For the sake of simplicity and because the strains in the fiber are very small, only interphase and matrix are considered for the determination of the mechanical interphase parameters (see Fig 2.).

The aim here is to determine the mechanical properties of the interphase with a tensile test. For symmetry reasons, only a quarter of the specimen is processed with the VFM. For the construction of the special virtual fields, the working zone, delimited with dashed lines in Fig.2, is divided into zones. The number of zones depends on the number of unknown mechanical parameters.

Fig. 2: Choice of the working zone

CONSTRUCTION OF THE SPECIAL VIRTUAL FIELDS

1 Constraints under which the special virtual fields must be built

Let us now examine the properties that the special virtual fields $\hat{\mathbf{u}}^*$ must satisfy to be determined. As explained in Grédiac et al. [6], those fields must obey two conditions:

- **Condition 1:** the special virtual fields must be kinematically admissible. Hence,

$$\forall M \in S_u, \hat{\mathbf{u}}^*(M) = 0 \quad (9)$$

In the present approach, S_u is the boundary of the working zone (see Fig.3).

- **Condition 2:** for each unknown stiffness, the special virtual fields must verify Eqs.5-8.

2 Choice of the special virtual fields

The working zone is divided into zones in such a way that the number of nodes inside the working zone is equal or greater than the number of mechanical parameters to be determined. As an example, Fig 3 shows 6 zones with 2 nodes (so four unknowns) inside the working zone. Each special virtual field $\hat{\mathbf{u}}^*$ is continuous inside each element of the working zone.

Fig. 3: Spatial discretization of the working zone

Fig. 4: Element of the working zone

It is proposed to write the special virtual displacement fields in the each element of the working zone with monomials. Interpolation functions used in the usual finite element method are well suited to respect condition 1. Indeed, it is possible to write the special virtual fields equal to zero along the boundary and so at each node circled with white circles in Fig 3. The unknowns of the problem are then the radial and orthoradial virtual displacements of the points shown as black circles in Fig.3. These virtual displacements lead to the virtual field and therefore to the unknown rigidities according to Eq. (5)-(8). Linear functions are used in the present work. With polar coordinates (r,θ) , the interpolation functions on an element e (see Fig. 4) are written as follows:

$$\varphi_A(r,\theta) = \frac{(r-r_C)(\theta-\theta_C)}{(r_A-r_C)(\theta_A-\theta_C)} \quad (10)$$

$$\varphi_B(r,\theta) = -\frac{(r-r_D)(\theta-\theta_D)}{(r_A-r_C)(\theta_A-\theta_C)} \quad (11)$$

$$\varphi_C(r, \theta) = \frac{(r - r_A)(\theta - \theta_A)}{(r_A - r_C)(\theta_A - \theta_C)} \quad (12)$$

$$\varphi_D(r, \theta) = -\frac{(r - r_B)(\theta - \theta_B)}{(r_A - r_C)(\theta_A - \theta_C)} \quad (13)$$

Components of special virtual field $\hat{\mathbf{u}}^* = \hat{u}_r^* \vec{e}_r + \hat{u}_\theta^* \vec{e}_\theta$ on an element e are written as follows:

$$\hat{u}_r^*(r, \theta) = \varphi_A(r, \theta) \hat{u}_{rA}^* + \varphi_B(r, \theta) \hat{u}_{rB}^* + \varphi_C(r, \theta) \hat{u}_{rC}^* + \varphi_D(r, \theta) \hat{u}_{rD}^* \quad (14)$$

$$\hat{u}_\theta^*(r, \theta) = \varphi_A(r, \theta) \hat{u}_{\theta A}^* + \varphi_B(r, \theta) \hat{u}_{\theta B}^* + \varphi_C(r, \theta) \hat{u}_{\theta C}^* + \varphi_D(r, \theta) \hat{u}_{\theta D}^* \quad (15)$$

The special virtual strain components on an element e are easily deduced by differentiation of the special virtual displacement field:

$$\left\{ \begin{aligned} \hat{\varepsilon}_{rr}^* &= \frac{\partial \hat{u}_r^*}{\partial r} = \frac{\hat{u}_{rA}^*(\theta - \theta_c) - \hat{u}_{rB}^*(\theta - \theta_D) + \hat{u}_{rC}^*(\theta - \theta_A) - \hat{u}_{rD}^*(\theta - \theta_B)}{(r_A - r_C)(\theta_A - \theta_c)} \\ \hat{\varepsilon}_{\theta\theta}^* &= \frac{1}{r} \left(\frac{\partial \hat{u}_\theta^*}{\partial \theta} + \hat{u}_r^* \right) = \frac{1}{r} \left(\frac{\hat{u}_{\theta A}^*(r - r_c) - \hat{u}_{\theta B}^*(r - r_D) + \hat{u}_{\theta C}^*(r - r_A) - \hat{u}_{\theta D}^*(r - r_B)}{(r_A - r_C)(\theta_A - \theta_c)} \right) \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{r} \left(\frac{\hat{u}_{rA}^*(r - r_c)(\theta - \theta_c) - \hat{u}_{rB}^*(r - r_D)(\theta - \theta_D) + \hat{u}_{rC}^*(r - r_A)(\theta - \theta_A) - \hat{u}_{rD}^*(r - r_B)(\theta - \theta_B)}{(r_A - r_C)(\theta_A - \theta_c)} \right) \\ \hat{\varepsilon}_{r\theta}^* &= \frac{1}{2r} \frac{\partial \hat{u}_\theta^*}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{2r} \left(\frac{\partial \hat{u}_r^*}{\partial \theta} - \hat{u}_\theta^* \right) = \frac{1}{2r} \left(\frac{\hat{u}_{\theta A}^*(\theta - \theta_c) - \hat{u}_{\theta B}^*(\theta - \theta_D) + \hat{u}_{\theta C}^*(\theta - \theta_A) - \hat{u}_{\theta D}^*(\theta - \theta_B)}{(r_A - r_C)(\theta_A - \theta_c)} \right) \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{2r} \left(\frac{\hat{u}_{rA}^*(r - r_c) - \hat{u}_{rB}^*(r - r_D) + \hat{u}_{rC}^*(r - r_A) - \hat{u}_{rD}^*(r - r_B)}{(r_A - r_C)(\theta_A - \theta_c)} \right) \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{2r} \left(\frac{-\hat{u}_{\theta A}^*(r - r_c)(\theta - \theta_c) + \hat{u}_{\theta B}^*(r - r_D)(\theta - \theta_D) - \hat{u}_{\theta C}^*(r - r_A)(\theta - \theta_A) + \hat{u}_{\theta D}^*(r - r_B)(\theta - \theta_B)}{(r_A - r_C)(\theta_A - \theta_c)} \right) \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (16)$$

3 Assembly process

The next step consists in assembling the different elements of the interphase on one hand, and of the matrix on the other hand. As illustrated in the example in Fig.3, three elements must be assembled in the interphase and in the matrix too. Taking into account zero virtual displacement along the boundary of the working zone, only 4 displacements remain unknown: $\hat{u}_{rC}^{*(1)}$, $\hat{u}_{rC}^{*(2)}$, $\hat{u}_{\theta C}^{*(1)}$ and $\hat{u}_{\theta C}^{*(2)}$. Each integral $\int_{V_i} \varepsilon_i \varepsilon_j^* dV$ on the interphase on one hand and $\int_{V_m} \varepsilon_i \varepsilon_j^* dV$ in the matrix in the other hand can be written as follows:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \int_{V_i} \varepsilon_i \hat{\varepsilon}_j^* dV = e \sum_{k=1}^3 \left(\int_{S_i^{(k)}} \varepsilon_{i(k)} \hat{\varepsilon}_{j(k)}^* dS \right) \\ \int_{V_m} \varepsilon_i \hat{\varepsilon}_j^* dV = e \sum_{k=4}^6 \left(\int_{S_m^{(k)}} \varepsilon_{i(k)} \hat{\varepsilon}_{j(k)}^* dS \right) \end{array} \right. \quad (17)$$

where e is the thickness of the specimen, $S_i^{(k)}$ and $S_m^{(k)}$ are respectively the external surface of element k of the interphase and of the matrix. $\varepsilon_{i(k)}$ and $\hat{\varepsilon}_{j(k)}^*$ are respectively the real strain components and the virtual ones of each element k .

4. Final linear system

In conclusion to the above section, a system of 4 linear equations where $\hat{u}_{rC}^*(1)$, $\hat{u}_{rC}^*(2)$, $\hat{u}_{\theta C}^*(1)$ and $\hat{u}_{\theta C}^*(2)$ are unknown is obtained. For instance the four unknowns of a special virtual field leading to $Q_{rr}^{(i)}$ verify the following system:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \hat{u}_{rC}^*(1)[R\theta A(1) - R\theta B(2)] + \hat{u}_{rC}^*(2)[R\theta A(2) - R\theta B(3)] = 1 \\ \hat{u}_{rC}^*(1)[\theta R\theta A(1) - \theta R\theta B(2)] + \hat{u}_{rC}^*(2)[\theta R\theta A(2) - \theta R\theta B(3)] + \hat{u}_{\theta C}^*(1)[\theta R A(1) - \theta R B(2)] + \hat{u}_{\theta C}^*(2)[\theta R A(2) - \theta R B(3)] = 0 \\ \hat{u}_{rC}^*(1)[RR\theta A(1) - RR\theta B(2) + \theta\theta A(1) - \theta\theta B(2)] + \hat{u}_{rC}^*(2)[RR\theta A(2) - RR\theta B(3) + \theta\theta A(2) - \theta\theta B(3)] \\ + \hat{u}_{\theta C}^*(1)[RRA(1) - RRB(2)] + \hat{u}_{\theta C}^*(2)[RRA(2) - RRB(3)] = 0 \\ \hat{u}_{rC}^*(1)[R\theta R A(1) - R\theta R B(2)] + \hat{u}_{rC}^*(2)[R\theta R A(2) - R\theta R B(3)] \\ + \hat{u}_{\theta C}^*(1)[R\theta\theta A(1) - R\theta\theta B(2) - R\theta R\theta A(1) + R\theta R\theta B(2)] + \hat{u}_{\theta C}^*(2)[R\theta\theta A(1) - R\theta\theta B(2) - R\theta R\theta A(1) + R\theta R\theta B(2)] = 0 \end{array} \right. \quad (18)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} R\theta X(j) &= \frac{\int_{S_i^{(j)}} \varepsilon_r (\theta - \theta_X^{(j)}) dS}{(r_A^{(j)} - r_C^{(j)})(\theta_A^{(j)} - \theta_C^{(j)})}, \quad \theta R\theta X(j) = \frac{\int_{S_i^{(j)}} \varepsilon_\theta (r - r_X^{(j)})(\theta - \theta_X^{(j)}) dS}{r(r_A^{(j)} - r_C^{(j)})(\theta_A^{(j)} - \theta_C^{(j)})}, \quad \theta R X(j) = \frac{\int_{S_i^{(j)}} \varepsilon_\theta (r - r_X^{(j)}) dS}{r(r_A^{(j)} - r_C^{(j)})(\theta_A^{(j)} - \theta_C^{(j)})}, \\ RR\theta X(j) &= \frac{\int_{S_i^{(j)}} \varepsilon_r (r - r_X^{(j)})(\theta - \theta_X^{(j)}) dS}{(r_A^{(j)} - r_C^{(j)})(\theta_A^{(j)} - \theta_C^{(j)})}, \quad \theta\theta X(j) = \frac{\int_{S_i^{(j)}} \varepsilon_\theta (\theta - \theta_X^{(j)}) dS}{(r_A^{(j)} - r_C^{(j)})(\theta_A^{(j)} - \theta_C^{(j)})}, \quad R R X(j) = \frac{\int_{S_i^{(j)}} \varepsilon_r (r - r_X^{(j)}) dS}{(r_A^{(j)} - r_C^{(j)})(\theta_A^{(j)} - \theta_C^{(j)})}, \\ R\theta R X(j) &= \frac{\int_{S_i^{(j)}} \frac{2\varepsilon_{r\theta} (r - r_X^{(j)})}{r} dS}{r(r_A^{(j)} - r_C^{(j)})(\theta_A^{(j)} - \theta_C^{(j)})}, \quad R\theta\theta X(j) = \frac{\int_{S_i^{(j)}} 2\varepsilon_{r\theta} (\theta - \theta_X^{(j)}) dS}{(r_A^{(j)} - r_C^{(j)})(\theta_A^{(j)} - \theta_C^{(j)})}, \quad R\theta R\theta X(j) = \frac{\int_{S_i^{(j)}} \frac{2\varepsilon_{r\theta} (r - r_X^{(j)})(\theta - \theta_X^{(j)})}{r} dS}{(r_A^{(j)} - r_C^{(j)})(\theta_A^{(j)} - \theta_C^{(j)})} \end{aligned}$$

($X=A, B, C$ or D and $j=1, 2$ or 3)

The four unknowns $\hat{u}_{rC}^*(1)$, $\hat{u}_{rC}^*(2)$, $\hat{u}_{\theta C}^*(1)$ and $\hat{u}_{\theta C}^*(2)$ of the special virtual fields leading to the other stiffness parameters are determined by changing the location of the “1” in the right hand of system (18).

NUMERICAL SIMULATIONS

1. Finite element model

Since the paper focuses on the identification method and on the automatic determination of the virtual fields, no experimental data are presently processed. The strain fields are obtained with finite element simulations. The materials tested are reported in Table 1 for the matrix and the fibre and in Table 2 for the interphase. The behaviour of the matrix and the fibre is isotropic. The first interphase considered exhibits an orthotropic behaviour, the second one an isotropic behaviour and the third one an isotropic behaviour with a linear evolution of Young's modulus along the radius. E_{int} and E_{ext} are respectively Young's modulus at R_f and at R_i . The strain fields corresponding to the three materials are obtained with the ANSYS package.

Material	E (MPa)	ν
Matrix	3000	0.3
Fibre	72000	0.3

Table 1: Mechanical parameters of the matrix and the fibres

Material	Q_{rr} (MPa)	$Q_{\theta\theta}$ (MPa)	$Q_{r\theta}$	Q_{ss} (MPa)
1	3640.4	1560.2	468.1	500.0
2	2747.2	2747.2	824.2	961.5

Material	E_{int} (MPa)	E_{ext} (MPa)	ν
3	2000	4000	0.3

Table 2: Mechanical parameters of the interphase

The mesh of the active zone has $(8+8)*96=1536$ quadrilateral linear elements in the first and third case and $(8+16)*100=2400$ quadrilateral linear elements in the second case.

2. Results for an orthotropic behaviour of the interphase

2.1 Results without and with noise

Results obtained for specimen 1 are reported in Table 3 with a size of each quarter defined by angles $a=\pi/4$, $b=\pi/8$ and $c=\pi/8$ (see Fig.3). A uniform random noise is added to the input data to observe the sensitivity of the procedure to a noise. The magnitude is a percentage $p\%$ of the maximum value of the absolute value of the three strains. 30 different calculations have been performed, each of them with a new set of randomly generated noisy strain components:

Material 1		Q_{rr} (MPa)	$Q_{\theta\theta}$ (MPa)	$Q_{r\theta}$ (MPa)	Q_{ss} (MPa)
Reference		3640.4	1560.2	468.1	500.0
p=0%	Value	3640.3	1573.6	467.5	499.7
	%	-0.003%	0.9%	-0.1%	-0.06%
p=1%	Mean value	3641.2	1667.2	456.7	496.9
	%	0.02%	6.8%	-2.4%	-0.6%
p=4%	Mean value	3646.9	2252.5	378.6	478.4
	%	0.2%	44.4%	-19.1%	-4.3%

Table 3: Identified stiffnesses, material 1

When looking at the results obtained from "exact" data, the relative error is less than 1%, validating the numerical identification routine. The $Q_{\theta\theta}$ and $Q_{r\theta}$ terms are very sensitive to noise, contrary to the Q_{rr} and Q_{ss} terms.

2.2 Sensitivity to the size of the active zones.

The size of each zone is an important parameter for the identification of the mechanical stiffnesses of the interphase (see Table 4). The same remarks as in the previous section can be made. The Q_{rr} and Q_{ss} terms are rather insensitive to the size of the quarters, contrary to the $Q_{\theta\theta}$ and $Q_{r\theta}$ terms. The sensitivity seems to be more important when angles a and c are equals.

Material 1	Q_{rr} (MPa)	$Q_{\theta\theta}$ (MPa)	$Q_{r\theta}$	Q_{ss} (MPa)
Reference	3640,4	1560,2	468,1	500
$a=\pi/4, b=\pi/8, c=\pi/8$	3640,3	1573,6	467,5	499,7
%	-0,003%	0,86%	-0,13%	-0,06%
$a=\pi/8, b=\pi/4, c=\pi/8$	3637	1266,5	501,9	508,9
%	-0,09%	-18,82%	7,22%	1,78%
$a=\pi/8, b=\pi/8, c=\pi/4$	3640,3	1573,6	467,5	499,7
%	-0,003%	0,86%	-0,13%	-0,06%
$a=\pi/6, b=\pi/6, c=\pi/6$	3639	1446,9	481,7	503,5
%	-0,04	-7,26	2,91	0,7

Table 4: Identified stiffnesses, material 1

3. Results for an isotropic behaviour of the interphase

3.1 Results without and with noise

Results obtained for sample 2 are reported in Table 5 with a size of each quarter defined by the angles $a=\pi/4$, $b=\pi/4$ and $c=0$ (see Fig.3). Indeed, in the case of an elastic linear isotropic behaviour, only two material parameters are unknowns (Q_{rr} and $Q_{r\theta}$ for example). As a consequence, the working zone is divided into four quarters: two in the interphase zone, and two in the matrix zone. The same procedure as in the previous section has been applied in terms of sensitivity to noise.

Material 2	Q_{rr} (MPa)	$Q_{r\theta}$ (MPa)
Reference	2747.2	824.2
$p=0\%$ Value	2747.3	824.1
%	0.004%	-0.01%
$p=1\%$ Mean value	2747.0	823.5
%	-0.007%	-0.08%
$p=4\%$ Mean value	2746.5	823.5
%	-0.02%	-0.08%

Table 5: Identified stiffnesses, material 2

Contrary to the previous case, the mechanical parameters are rather insensitive to noise. In the case of a noise with a magnitude equal to 4%, the difference between identified stiffnesses and “exact” ones is less than 0.1%.

3.2 Sensitivity to the size of the active zones.

Contrary to the previous case, the stiffness components are not sensitive to the size of the quarters (see Table 6).

Material 2	Reference	$\pi/4, \pi/4$ %	$\pi/6, \pi/3$ %	$\pi/3, \pi/6$ %	$3\pi/8, \pi/8$ %	$\pi/8, 3\pi/8$ %
Q_{rr} (MPa)	2747.2	2747.3 0.004%	2755.6 0.31%	2741.5 -0.21%	2747.2 0.00%	2747.3 0.004%
$Q_{r\theta}$ (MPa)	824.2	824.1 -0.01%	824.7 0.06%	821.9 -0.28%	824.0 -0.02%	824.1 -0.01%

Table 6: Identified stiffnesses, material 2

4. Results for an isotropic behaviour of the interphase with spatially varying properties

4.1 Results without and with noise

In this section, the mechanical behaviour of the interphase is chosen isotropic with linear evolution of Young's modulus vs. radius. So, three material parameters are unknowns: E_{int} , E_{ext} and ν . Each node inside the working zone has two components: u_r and r_t . So the number of unknowns is always an even number. Two configurations have been tested. The first one is the same as for the orthotropic material. The second one consists in dividing the working zone in two parts for the matrix zone and in four parts for the interphase zone. The working zone is presented in Figure 5.

Fig. 5: Spatial discretization of the working zone

The first tested configuration (see Fig. 3) did not produce any result. This is due to the fact that the virtual strain components are constant along any radius of the working zone. The spatially varying modulus cannot be correctly taken into account.

Results obtained for material 3 and the second configuration (Fig. 5) are reported in Table 7 with a size of each zone defined by angles $a=\pi/4$, $b=\pi/4$ (Fig.5). Even without any noise, results are not satisfactory. This is certainly due to the fact that the number of material unknowns is less than the number of node components u_r and r_t inside the working zone.

Material 3		E_{int} (MPa)	E_{ext} (MPa)	ν
Reference		2000.0	4000.0	0.30
p=0%	Value	1709.7	4186.2	0.3997
	%	-14.51%	4.65%	33.23%
p=1%	Mean value	1709.3	4186.1	0.3993
	%	-14.53%	4.65%	33.1%
p=4%	Mean value	1709.6	4188.1	0.3997
	%	-14.52%	4.70%	33.23%

Table 7: Identified stiffnesses, material 3

CONCLUSION

The virtual fields method with special virtual fields allows a direct identification of parameters governing constitutive equations from heterogeneous strain fields. In this paper, the practical determination of the special virtual fields is carried out when the interphase mechanical properties of a composite material are to be determined. Some numerical simulations have been carried out to assess the feasibility, the accuracy and the stability of the method.

Special virtual fields defined by parts have been used in the paper. Satisfactory results have been obtained for elastic linear orthotropic and isotropic behaviour of the interphase. On the other hand, the spatial discretization of the working zone was not in agreement with the number of unknowns for the third material. As a consequence, identified stiffnesses were not in good agreement with the reference values. In the near future, another procedure will be used. It will consist in a much more important discretization of the working zone and a use of special virtual fields that minimize the influence of the noise measurement on the identified parameters.

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